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D3.2 – Training programme and knowledge sharing report

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Glossary of terms

Item	Description
ACE	Architects' Council of Europe
AEC	Architecture, Engineering, and Construction
AECO	Architecture, Engineering, Construction, and Operation
AI	Artificial Intelligence
BK	Bouwkunde (TU Delft's Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment)
BSI	British Standards Institution
EAAE	European Association for Architectural Education
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GNU	General Public License
HE	Higher Education
LAMA	Laboratory for Additive Manufacturing in Architecture
LCMS	Learning Content Management System
ML	Machine Learning
MOOC	Massive Online Open Course
NEB	New European Bauhaus
NEBA	New European Bauhaus Alliance
RISE	Research Institutes of Sweden
RTO	Registered Training Organisation
RWTA	Rheinisch-Westfälische Technische Hochschule Aachen
UPV	Universitat Politècnica de València
SURF	The ICT cooperative of Dutch education and research institutions
TU Delft	Delft University of Technology
VET	Vocational Education and Training

Keywords

Website, Directory, CMS, Copyright, Creative Commons, Open Science, Digital Ecosystem

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Executive Summary

This report outlines the digiNEB.eu training programme and platform, focusing on knowledge sharing and upskilling stakeholders in New European Bauhaus (NEB) communities in digital technology. The programme, delivered via an eLearning platform and live events, aimed to align with NEB Lighthouses, Labs, and DIH events.

However, the eLearning environment, described in the Grant application as the TRUST-LCMS, turned out to be Moodle, a free, open-source platform that was not suited for the task. This mismatch was one of the points that led to tensions, resulting in Trust-IT's departure in September 2023.

The report also discusses the emerging NEB Academy, an EU initiative to upskill the construction ecosystem for a regenerative, circular economy. The New European Bauhaus Academy Alliance, including DigiNEB partners, was selected to lead this effort.

The report emphasises the need for a robust platform to support the Academy, acknowledging the lack of ready-made solutions. It highlights trends in open education, which aims to reduce barriers to learning, modernise higher education, and bridge formal and non-formal education.

The NEB Academy targets a broad audience, including architects, engineers, and construction workers, requiring multilingual, cross-border training and recognition of skills through micro-credentials.

The DigiNEB project revealed the absence of suitable learning management systems that are up to this task, prompting TU Delft to develop DigiPedia, a platform for digital literacy in architecture and the built environment, launched in November 2024.

The report surveys the current landscape of digital literacy training, emphasising the need for tailored solutions to meet the diverse needs of the NEB community and construction sector. It illustrates how such needs can be met by providing an overview of DigiPedia.

Table of Contents

1. Context	6
The TRUST-LCMS product.....	6
NEB Academy	6
2. Point of Departure.....	8
2.1 Open Education	8
2.2 Beyond the NEB community.....	9
2.3 Beyond national borders	9
Local and European	9
Languages.....	9
Architect – a protected profession.....	9
Different backgrounds.....	9
The national scope of open education repositories.....	10
2.4 Life Long Learning, certificates and badges.....	10
2.5 Robust funding	10
2.6 DigiPedia: Digital Literacy for Architecture and the Built Environment	10
2.7 Current landscape	10
3. Current landscape	11
3.1 MOOCs	11
3.2 Courses by Research Institutes.....	13
3.3 Courses by EU initiatives	15
3.4 Industry Giants	19
3.5 Software related course offerings.....	20
3.6 Digital Literacy platform	21
4. Platform architecture	23
4.1 Digital technologies enable new ways of working	23
4.2 DigiPedia is a Platform about Digital Literacy.....	23
4.3 DigiPedia is an Open Education platform.....	23
4.4 Funding.....	24
4.5 Follow-up of proven approach	24
4.6 Open-Source platform, two components.....	24
TU Delft as an EU leading institute.....	24
Reason for change.....	24
4.7 Platform setup.....	24
4.8 Screenshots	25
5. Concluding remarks.....	36
List of Figures.....	37

1. Context

The task of deliverable 3.2, “**Training programme and knowledge sharing report,**” was to describe the digiNEB.eu training programme, including the eLearning Platform and online content strategy, as well as the training activities and results. It was formulated in the Grant Agreement as follows:

“DigiNEB.eu will provide efficient training programmes for co-creation between different categories of stakeholders by enabling effective knowledge transfer between digital research and NEB communities and providing them with the necessary knowledge, allowing them to upskill and become long-term beneficiaries of the project’s outcomes. The training programme will be delivered in both online and live environments, by alignment with NEB Lighthouses, NEB Labs and DIH events, through a dedicated project-branded eLearning training platform which will remain accessible after the project end.”

The TRUST-LCMS product

The eLearning environment mentioned above is referred to as an environment “*based on the TRUST-LCMS product, which will be provided with no licence costs by Trust-IT.*”

The eLearning environment that was put in place by Trust-IT, six months after the start of the project, was in fact not a dedicated tool developed by Trust-IT. Instead, it was Moodle. Moodle is a popular and “*free and open-source learning management system written in PHP and distributed under the GNU General Public License.*” Indeed, it was provided with no licence costs by Trust-IT, not out of generosity, but for the simple fact that Trust-IT does not hold the licence for this product.

The choice to install Moodle came out of the blue. The other project partners were not consulted. As such, the platform was not based on the identification of target groups, potential trainers, specific training programmes, learning objectives, or pedagogies. The mismatch between this IT-driven approach and the expectations of the educational partners was in part the reason why the partners decided to part ways in September 2023. It took until April 2024 before Trust-IT was willing to hand over the platform, all digital assets, the URLs, and the social media accounts. All that time, the remaining partnership was locked out of the website and platform.

NEB Academy

Early on in the DigiNEB project, the consortium was asked if it could provide the platform for hosting the NEB Academy, an initiative launched by EU President Ursula von der Leyen. This request was based on the assumption that the TRUST-LCMS product was real and would be up to the task.

Things moved rather quickly: late 2023, the idea of the NEB Academy evolved into an open call for a consortium that could prepare the launch of the NEB Academy.

The NEB Academy aims to accelerate “***up-skilling and re-skilling in the construction ecosystem, to support the transition from an extractive, mineral-based and fossil hydrocarbon-fuelled construction economy, to a regenerative bio-economy and circular system of material reuse.***”

The proposal by the New European Bauhaus Academy Alliance (led by the University of Primorska) was selected early in 2024. This Alliance will lay the foundation of the NEB Academy. Three partners of the DigiNEB project (EAAE, InnovaWood, and TU Delft) participate in the follow-up initiative.

Given the fast evolving context, this report outlines the contours and requirements of a platform that can facilitate the NEB Academy, accepting the fact that no out-of-the-box solutions exist. It also presents a training programme for Digital Literacy in Architecture and the Built Environment.

2. Point of Departure

Work Package 3 of the DigiNEB project aims to set up a training programme. To provide the input for such a programme, we conducted a quick scan to gain a better understanding of what is already available, what platforms exist, what courses have already been initiated, who the providers are, and what the broader trends in education are. Let's start with the latter: the trends and developments.

2.1 Open Education

As part of the development towards open science, there is a growing awareness that open education is essential for creating equity or societal justice, not just for classroom or campus education but for lifelong learning as well.

The European Commission's definition of open education is:

"a way of carrying out education, often using digital technologies. Its aim is to widen access and participation to everyone by removing barriers and making learning accessible, abundant, and customisable for all. It offers multiple ways of teaching and learning, building and sharing knowledge. It also provides a variety of access routes to formal and non-formal education, and connects"

(Opening up Education: A Support Framework for Higher Education Institutions, 2016)

The Commission stipulates the advantages of Open Education as:

- *First, it can help to reduce or remove barriers to education (e.g. cost, geography, time, entry requirements). This gives learners the opportunity to up skill or re-skill at a lower or nearly no cost, and in a flexible way.*
- *Second, it supports the modernisation of higher education in Europe, since contemporary open education is largely carried out via digital technologies.*
- *Finally, it opens up the possibility of bridging non-formal and formal education. This can take place if HE institutions and other accredited institutions recognised the credentials they each issue to learners.*
- (https://joint-research-centre.ec.europa.eu/what-open-education_en)

In open science programmes in academia more advantages are mentioned, such as:

- Open Education opens up the opportunity to jointly develop educational resources by remixing, transforming, and building upon shared materials.
- Open Education provides the opportunity for educators to gain recognition when the open educational resources that they have created are used by an increasing community of learners throughout Europe.

However, opening up education is a process of cultural change, and that may take time. Not every organisation is immediately ready to take this step into the unknown. Enforcing 'open education' could stifle a project or initiative. Stimulating and facilitating is a better approach. The educational support systems we put in place today should provide the option to share resources and be ready to facilitate open practices. Requiring that learners must register, log in, and pay should be a thing of the past. Barriers to information should be kept to a minimum. Registration, however, will be necessary when certification is required.

2.2 Beyond the NEB community

The New European Bauhaus seeks to transform the way we design, plan, and build the environments we live in. In that context, the objective of the DigiNEB project is to bridge...

“the digital and NEB communities and raise awareness around EU digital solutions for all NEB stakeholders, establishing a pan-European digital ecosystem. With its lean action plan, digiNEB.eu enables Europe’s Green Deal ambition in designing & building greener and more inclusive living spaces for a better quality of life.”

Nonetheless, the ambition of enabling ‘Europe’s Green Deal’ requires that we focus on a broader audience than just the NEB community. This is reflected in the EC’s definition of the NEB Academy, which specifically refers to the ‘construction ecosystem’. It implies that the full architecture, engineering, and construction (AEC) sector participates, not just designers, planners, policymakers, and citizens, but also developers, investors, carpenters, and bricklayers.

2.3 Beyond national borders

Local and European

Typically, designers, planners, policymakers, and citizens work locally or nationally. The architectural design sector, for instance, obtains only a small percentage of its revenue abroad. This is due to the required detailed knowledge of national or regional rules and regulations, and to local client-designer relations.

Construction workers, on the other hand, display a high level of mobility due to labour shortages and wage differences between various European countries. Skills obtained in Bulgaria or Poland should be recognised in the Netherlands or Denmark, and vice versa.

Languages

The fact that vocational training is typically provided in national languages adds another requirement to a training programme as envisioned by the NEB Academy.

Architect – a protected profession

Although we need to look broader than just designers or architects, the architect does hold a key position in the construction ecosystem. Ensuring that architects are trained in digital skills and become digitally literate is essential.

The title of architect, however, is protected by the European Directive on the Recognition of Professional Qualifications. This necessitates that each member state registers who is qualified to call themselves an architect, based on training requirements that are formulated in official national regulations. If we aim for European schools and universities to embed digital literacy in their curricula, the best way is to make it a binding requirement for obtaining the title.

Different backgrounds

As we face a broad diversity of potential learners, ranging from vocationally to academically trained, speaking different languages, and previously exposed to a wide range of pedagogies and curricula, we have to anticipate that individuals will need to catch up on specific subjects or skills when we want to provide a specific training programme for larger groups.

The national scope of open education repositories

To implement the concept of open education requires a dedicated infrastructure where educators and trainers can upload, share, and download so-called Open Educational Resources (OER). Such facilities or repositories are being set up throughout Europe, but once more on a national or institutional level. Take, for instance, “**Edusources**” developed by SURF in the Netherlands, which describes itself as:

“the platform for digital (open) educational resources for Dutch education. The one-stop-shop with both educational resources and knowledge about creating, sharing, finding, and reusing digital educational resources.” (<https://edusources.nl>)

The platform is provided by means of an institutional login procedure and can be used by all Dutch universities, universities of applied sciences, and vocational training institutions, but not by other Dutch providers of training or by institutes elsewhere in Europe. This means that such national initiatives cannot yet be used for a broad European initiative like the NEB Academy. Additional solutions are required.

2.4 Life Long Learning, certificates and badges

The NEB Academy responds to the fact that learning doesn’t stop after leaving school or college. As society, the economy, and technology keep evolving, it is necessary to update previously acquired knowledge and learn new skills. To effectively offer courses or training, we need a European system that recognises the skills and knowledge obtained in these trainings by means of so-called micro-credentials and badges, issued by accredited educational institutes (e.g., members of the European Association for Architectural Education) or professional organisations (e.g., members of the Architects’ Council of Europe).

2.5 Robust funding

A broader implementation of lifelong learning requires that member states officially integrate lifelong learning into their policies and the ways they finance education.

2.6 DigiPedia: Digital Literacy for Architecture and the Built Environment

The DigiNEB project made us painfully aware that no out-of-the-box solution exists that can meet the complex needs of an initiative like DigiNEB or the NEB Academy. Learning management systems do exist, but they are mainly focused on regular curriculum-based classwork. To bridge this gap, TU Delft (the coordinator of the DigiNEB project) has started the development of a platform called DigiPedia. The platform was largely funded by the TU Delft Open Science Programme, led by Frank van der Hoeven (also coordinator of the DigiNEB project), while the development was led by Michela Turrin of the same Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment. DigiPedia was officially launched on 21 November 2024 and is designated to become the platform to be used for the NEB Academy.

2.7 Current landscape

Next, this document continues by providing a quick overview of the current landscape of training available. The overview closes with an in-depth discussion of DigiPedia.

3. Current landscape

The aim of this section is to provide an overview of the broad landscape of digital literacy for the NEB community and construction ecosystem. It is not the objective to be exhaustive; instead, we focus on gaining an understanding of the diversity of formats and providers, addressing MOOCs, courses by research institutes, EU initiatives, industry giants, and software-related courses, before moving to the platform for digital literacy. The overview below is included in the DigiNEB platform (complete with links to the sources).

3.1 MOOCs

The so-called Massive Open Online Courses gained especially popularity between 2008 and 2012. MOOCs are typically developed by established Institutes of Higher Education and aim at extra-curricular learning. edX is one of the prominent platforms used for distributing such MOOCs. edX offers 40 courses on sustainability and architecture developed by TU Delft, UPV, RWTH and others:

Sustainable Cities | SDG Academy

Sustainable Urban Development | Delft University of Technology

Sustainability in Architecture: An Interdisciplinary Introduction | Universitat Politècnica de València

Circular Fashion: Design, Science and Value in a Sustainable Clothing Industry | Wageningen University & Research

Circular Economy for a Sustainable Built Environment | Delft University of Technology

Living Heritage and Sustainable Development | SDG Academy

Zero-Energy Design: an approach to make your building sustainable | Delft University of Technology

Co-Creating Sustainable Cities | Delft University of Technology

Built environment sustainability assessment | Universitat Politècnica de València

Decarbonization of Heat – An Introduction to Sustainable Heating and Cooling Systems | Delft University of Technology

Water Works: Activating Heritage for Sustainable Development | Delft University of Technology

Sustainable Building Design | Massachusetts Institute of Technology

Sustainable Building with Timber | Delft University of Technology

Sustainable Transformation of Cities and Regions | RWTH Aachen University

Sustainable Urban Environments | Trinity College

Japanese Architecture and Structural Design | Tokyo Institute of Technology

Urban Ecology Design | Delft University of Technology

(Re)Imagining Port Cities: Understanding Space, Society and Culture | Delft University of Technology

Responsible Innovation and Circular Fashion | SDA Bocconi School of Management

Circular Fashion Business Models | SDA Bocconi School of Management

Façade design and engineering: complexity made simple | Delft University of Technology

Global Housing Design | Delft University of Technology

Site Planning Online | Massachusetts Institute of Technology

Nature-based Urban Regeneration | RWTH Aachen University

རིག་གནས་བསྐྱུ་འཇུག་དང་ཉར་ཚགས་བྱེད་པའི་ཐབས་ལམ་མདོར་བསྐྱུ་མ། | **Methods and Techniques for Documenting and Preserving Tibetan Culture** | The Smithsonian Institution

Interpreting Vernacular Architecture in Asia | The University of Hong Kong

Efficient HVAC Systems | Delft University of Technology

Energy Demand in Buildings | Delft University of Technology

Energy Supply Systems for Buildings | Delft University of Technology

Comfort and Health in Buildings | Delft University of Technology

Advanced Timber Plate Structural Design | École polytechnique fédérale de Lausanne

Cultural Heritage in Transformation | RWTH Aachen University

Infrastructure Management for Public Libraries | The University of Michigan

Urban Design for the Public Good: Dutch Urbanism | Delft University of Technology

Rethink the City: New approaches to Global and Local Urban Challenges | Delft University of Technology

Building Inclusive Cities: Tackling Urban Inequality and Segregation | Delft University of Technology

Principles, Materials and Technologies of Façades | Delft University of Technology

Detailing Stick-System Façades: A Practical Approach | Delft University of Technology

Ecodesign for Cities and Suburbs | University of British Columbia

Developing Digital Transition Strategies for Cultural Heritage Institutions | KU Leuven

3.2 Courses by Research Institutes

Institutes of Higher Education are not just the only providers of extra-curricular education. RISE (Research Institutes of Sweden) and the BSI (British Standards Institution) for instance are active as well in providing courses and trainings that are relevant to the NEB community. Contrary to MOOCs, most of these courses are not open and charge a substantial fee:

RISE

(<https://www.ri.se/en/what-we-do/educations>)

Courses about moisture protection in buildings

Training - Business driven climate transition

Stormwater and Cloudburst Coordinator (basic cours)

Training program for Innovation Managers

Learn how to calculate the fire resistance of timber structures

Innovation Management for Executive Teams, according to ISO 56001

Sustainability strategies for the built environmental sector

Knowledge-enhancing through lectures for the construction industry

AI for Everyone: An Introduction on Your Terms

Lecture - Enhance by-product use via industrial and urban symbiosis

Lecture - Challenges in managing municipal development

Energy Supply and Physical Planning

Course about reflective leadership in a changing society

Sustainable and circular product lifetime

Inclusive urban planning

Design process for green transition

Basic course for moisture technicians and moisture damage investigators

Introduction to Life Cycle Assessment, LCA

Energy Efficiency - Cooling and Heat Pump Technology in One System

Migraine-Friendly Lighting

Basic course for moisture technicians and moisture damage investigators

BSI

(<https://www.bsigroup.com/en-GB/products-and-services/training-courses-and-qualifications/training-courses-results>)

BIM Fundamentals Training Course

BIM ISO 19650 Part 2: Project Delivery Training Course

Building Information Modelling (BIM) ISO 19650 Part 3

Information Exchange Training Course - BIM ISO 19650 Part 4:

BIM ISO 19650 Part 5: Security and BIM Training Course

BIM PAS 1192 Part 6: Health and Safety Training Course

BIM Awareness On Demand Training Course

Collaborative Building Information Modelling (BIM)

Collaborative BIM: Senior Management Workshop Training Course

3.3 Courses by EU initiatives

EU funded projects have developed a number of interesting course platforms as well.

EU Citizen Science

One prominent platform is EU Citizen Science that describes itself as: *“a globally connected, inclusive and strong citizen science community for societal change in Europe.”*

(https://eu-citizen.science/training_resources)

Citizen Science and Artificial Intelligence Technologies: Collaborating for an Innovative and Unbiased Future

Overview of learning opportunities: Citizen Science

Monitoring and evaluating the impact of Citizen Science Hubs (CSHs)

What transformations are needed for research institutes to support citizen science?

Citizen Science in the dialogue between Science and Society

Driving changes to embed Citizen Science at your institution

Ethical aspects of Citizen Science: good practices and institutional interventions

The Citizen Science Funding Landscape

Citizen Science Hubs explained: needs, resources, best practices

Opening research to society in Horizon Europe. How to set up citizen science projects?

EUTOPIA Citizen Science Starter Kit

The Librarian's Guide to Citizen Science

Introduction to Citizen Science

Citizen Science Typologies

Designing for learning through citizen science

Your Right to Privacy Online

Storytelling for citizen science

Citizen Science Projects: How to Make a Difference (Part 1, 2, 3, 4)

Citizen Science in the Classroom: A toolkit

Phenology recording with young children

Co-created Citizen Science recording with older people

Volunteers in Citizen Science Projects

English Introduction to CS

Wildlife recording with participants with complex support needs

Citizen Science for everyone: A guide for teachers and support providers

Citizen Science and the Environment: Ideas for your Duke of Edinburgh's Award

Lessons from citizen science for community engagement practice

Citizen Science – Motivations, Progression and Accreditation

A Guide to using Social Media in your Citizen Science Project

Citizen Science in Your Community: A Guide to Getting Involved

Kutatónak a 'Citizen Science' megközelítésben rejlő lehetőségekről

Foundations of Citizen Science

Libraries as Community Hubs for Citizen Science

Science Communication MOOC

Citizen Science and Storytelling
English Communication

Training programs to build capacity for collaborative innovation processes

Estrategias y herramientas de comunicación aplicadas a proyectos de ciencia ciudadana

Citizen Science in Schools: schools as agents of community well-being through science and research

Research integrity, ethics and the SDGs within the context of citizen science (RIECS)

Bürger schaffen Klima Wissen

Empowerment through co-designed Citizen Science in education
English Engagement

Doing citizen science as open science: what, why and how
English Best practices

Basic regulations and ethics for citizen science

Evaluation and Impact Assessment in Citizen Science Projects

Social media management for citizen science projects

Volunteer engagement, management and care

Začnime si s občianskou vedou (Let's start with the citizen science)

GEOVACUI-2: Citizen Science for knowledge depopulation (didactic unit)

Train-the-trainer course on Marine Litter Education | Ocean Literacy

Introduction to Citizen Science for Journalists

MOOC "Have you seen an alien?"

Citizen Science with Geographic Information Systems and associated technologies (GIS&T)

Citizen Science and Scientific Crowdsourcing: an Introduction

Citizen Science Projects: How to Make a Difference

Open Science Training Handbook

Community Planning Toolkit

Californian Academy Sciences Citizen Science Toolkit: Teaching Science Through Citizen Science

Natural History Museum Guide to Citizen Science

Australian Citizen Science Association Youtube channel

Notes on Mobile: Launching a Workflow

CSA Webinar: Approaching Informed Consent in Citizen Science: Legal and Ethical Issues

CSA Webinar: Introducing the Law and Policy Working Group Source
English Regulations and ethics

CSA WEBINAR: Wide Angle Lens of Volunteer Engagement with UMN Extension

A Scientist's Guide to Citizen Science:

Book "The Field Guide to Citizen Science"

Forest Service Citizen Science Resource List

Citizen Science, An Introduction

Project Based Learning, Participatory Science, Education and Sustainable Development Goals

BRITEC MOOC: A Roadmap to Citizen Science Education
English Best practices

Enhancing youth learning through Community and Citizen Science: a guide for practitioners

WOODigital Learning Platform

The WOODigital platform: *“nurtures a generation of young Europeans, students, professionals, but also VET centres, RTOs and companies, and provide them with skills and competences required by the wood and furniture job market undergoing a transformative digitization process.”*

(<https://course.woodigital.eu>)

Introduction of Industry 4.0 and digitized workplaces

Introduction to software 4.0

Introduction to 4.0 machinery

Introduction to manufacturing management

Introduction to Circular Economy

Industry 4.0 for European SMEs: Challenges and opportunities

Computer aided design and manufacturing

Finishing systems

Manufacturing management systems

Ecodesign

Industry 4.0 in practice

Augmented reality - Virtual reality

Additive technologies

Software systems for management

Sustainable materials

Industry 4.0 - Case study

Software - Case study

Machinery - Case study

Case Study - Manufacturing management

Case Study - Ecodesign Approaches

3.4 Industry Giants

A well-established industry giant like Google operates the learning platform Kaggle “to share, stress test, and stay up-to-date on all the latest ML techniques and technologies. Discover a huge repository of community-published models, data & code for your next project.”

(<https://www.kaggle.com/learn>)

Intro to Programming

Python

Intro to Machine Learning

Pandas

Intermediate Machine Learning

Data Visualization

Feature Engineering

Intro to SQL

Advanced SQL

Intro to Deep Learning

Computer Vision

Time Series

Data Cleaning

Intro to AI Ethics

Geospatial Analysis

Machine Learning Explainability

Intro to Game AI and Reinforcement Learning

3.5 Software related course offerings

Next to the large organisations that offer training, there are also smaller applied offerings, such as Learn Visual Programming, a two-person initiative that provides training and tutorials related to the Grasshopper plugins they have developed themselves.

Interestingly, the size of this initiative is very similar to that of a typical architecture office. Still, the software developed by Learn Visual Programming is downloaded over 150,000 times and deserves to be taken seriously.

(<https://www.learn-visual-programming.com>)

NGON – Introduction

OpenNest – Digital Fabrication

How To? – Tutorials

3.6 Digital Literacy platform

DigiPedia is a unique initiative providing “*open educational tutorials on software and digital processes to support learning at TU Delft and encourage life-long learners around the world.*”

The platform offers courses and tutorials for software, subjects and lab environments and can function as a model for a learning environment to support the NEB Academy.

(<https://digipedia.tudelft.nl/>)

Courses

Vorm en overdracht

Digitale ontwerpomgeving

Bouwkunde als wetenschap

Computational Intelligence for Integrated Design

Fundamentals in Artificial Intelligence

Software

ANSYS

ArcGIS

BIM360

Grasshopper

Honeybee

Jupyter Notebook

Ladybug

PDOK

PUG

Python

QGIS

Revit

Rhino

Speckle

Wallacei

Subjects

3D Modelling

AI & ML

Analysis & simulation

Collaboration

Geospatial and Geographic Information Systems

Robot Programming

Parametric Modelling

Labs

BK Renderfarm

VR Lab

LAMA Lab

4. Platform architecture

In the previous chapters, we outlined the broad offering of courses and training by a wide variety of providers, ranging from IT giants to micro-enterprises. A coherent framework or training programme is lacking. To bridge this gap, TU Delft has developed a dedicated open-source platform for Digital Literacy in Architecture and the Built Environment: DigiPedia.

4.1 Digital technologies enable new ways of working

Digital Transformation is the transformation of processes and competencies by leveraging the potentials and impacts of digital technologies. The Architecture, Engineering, Construction, and Operation (AECO) industry is rapidly undergoing a Digital Transformation and seeks professionals able to position themselves in this change and to drive it by implementing its new directions. To understand the means, processes, and outcomes of the Digital Transformation, AECO professionals need Digital Literacy, which refers to the understanding of digital information based on technical skills and knowledge. Higher Education should be at the forefront, equipping new generations of students with the required knowledge, skills, and experience, as well as offering learning opportunities for professionals.

In coordination with the Educational Programmes at the TU Delft Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment (BK), DigiPedia is a platform that aims to facilitate training in the AECO domain regarding Digital Literacy. The project intends to create a reference environment that enables students to navigate the online teaching material useful in the general context of digitalisation, and specifically for the BK Education. The educational material is implemented and disseminated according to Open Education principles and is thus easily accessible also to current professionals.

4.2 DigiPedia is a Platform about Digital Literacy.

It collects tutorials and educational material on computational methods, techniques, and tools. It supports education in Architecture and the Built Environment on content related to “Digital” – from the basics of software tutorials to the advanced features of programming, developing machine learning models, AI techniques, etc. Teachers can upload various types of educational material (text, images, videos, code, etc.) and publish it via the DigiPedia teachers’ dashboard. Via the public DigiPedia front page, students can navigate through the educational material *per course* (BSc and various MSc tracks), *per subject* (e.g. Simulations; GIS; Parametric Modelling; Machine Learning; etc.), *per software* (e.g. QGIS, Rhino, Grasshopper, etc.) and, when relevant, *per BK LAB*.

4.3 DigiPedia is an Open Education platform.

The educational material is stored in SURF Sharekit and publicly shared according to the principles of Open Education, which makes it available also outside TU Delft. This allows benefits in knowledge dissemination worldwide (FYI: Its predecessor, TOI-Pedia, received about 1 million hits per year over a decade). The Open Education Programme at TU Delft is designed to foster the adoption and adaptation of teaching and learning methods through open educational resources. The programme aims to make education more accessible and affordable for students by building on existing practices.

4.4 Funding

DigiPedia is funded by the BK Quality Agreement (*Kwaliteitsafspraken Projecten*) from TU Delft's Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment, and by the Open Science Funding from the TU Delft Library. The platform is open-source, making it possible for other faculties and universities to deploy their own online tutorial platforms.

4.5 Follow-up of proven approach

DigiPedia is the follow-up of TOI-pedia: *"a digital repository of course material, tutorials, and software documentation related to the application of ICT in Architecture, Design and education"* which was in place since 2006 and got about 1 million hits per year.

4.6 Open-Source platform, two components

DigiPedia should be understood as two components. First, it is a dedicated platform that is developed as an open-source application (using the MIT license) and can be used for various other applications, like the NEB Academy. Second, it can be understood as a structured collection of open educational resources (OER) and tutorials (training programme) that can be accessed by students around the world, while it supports also the curriculum at TU Delft's Faculty of Architecture and the Built Environment.

TU Delft as an EU leading institute

A quick word why TU Delft matters in this case. TU Delft as a Dutch university ranks 3rd worldwide in the *QS World University Rankings by Subject 2024: Architecture & Built Environment*. Within the European Union TU Delft ranks number 1 in the same ranking.

Reason for change

After TOI-pedia served a global community of learners for more than a decade, both the platform and the content were due for an overhaul. More specifically:

- students requested to be supported in software learning;
- teachers needed to focus class-time on content;
- (new) students needed to fill background gaps at their own pace.

4.7 Platform setup

The new setup for DigiPedia therefore includes:

- tutorials to help students refine their **software skills**;
- educational material on **computational methods and techniques** to grasp rationale;
- **open education principles** for learning materials to be reusable and widely accessible.

As such the content is grouped in four categories:

- courses: tutorials that align with the needs of specific educational courses;
- subjects: tailored tutorials based on key subject areas;
- software: tutorials based on selected software tools;
- labs: tutorials for the use of equipment and tools in lab environments.

The platform provides a login option for system administrators and teachers/trainers that allows them to perform administrative tasks and:

- to update existing content;
- to create new content;
- to incorporate blended learning techniques.

Educators are provided with a:

- a custom teacher dashboard;
- user friendly interface to create and edit pages;
- easy navigation and use of uploaded media.

The platform features currently:

- text styling;
- tables with styling;
- term definitions;
- equations;
- command blocks;
- integrated code blocks;
- images;
- videos;
- tutorial card links;
- info blocks;
- quizzes;
- download files;
- h5p videos [interactive video elements];
- embedded external videos.

Planned features for 2025 include:

- multiple authors per tutorial;
- a draft page next to a published page;
- an improved layout for introduction pages;
- a student log-in;
- bookmarks;
- watch history and resume video.

4.8 Screenshots

To illustrate the platform, we provide a series of screenshots made on a tablet device:

Fig 4.7.1: Digipedia landing page

Fig 4.7.2: Overview of the four categories of tutorials in DigiPedia

Fig 4.7.3: Course overview with Master courses selected

The screenshot shows a mobile browser interface for the DigiPedia website. At the top, the browser status bar shows the time 20:47, date Sun 12 Jan, and 100% battery. The address bar contains 'digipedia.tudelft.nl'. The website header features the 'DigiPedia' logo and a search icon. The main content area is divided into two columns. The left column contains a sidebar with a 'Fundamentals of Artificial Intelligence' section, which is expanded to show a list of topics: 'Intro' (1 min), 'Deep Learning in Architecture' (1 min), 'Supervised Learning' (1 min), 'Unsupervised Learning' (1 min), and 'Other examples' (1 min). Below this is an 'Information' section with details: Course Code IFEEMCS520100, Last updated November 27, 2024, Keywords 'Artificial Intelligence' and 'CNN', Primary study 'Master', and Secondary study 'BK Master'. The right column features the course title 'Fundamentals of Artificial Intelligence 0/4' and 'Fundamentals of Artificial Intelligence'. Below the title is the subtitle 'Deep learning in Grasshopper' and a paragraph describing the course content. A 'Course tip' box contains an information icon and the text: 'Course tip: This is a course for an introduction to Deep Neural Networks and how to use them on Grasshopper'. Below this, a section titled 'You can find additional information here:' contains two buttons: 'Subject: Machine Learning' and 'Software: PUG', both with right-pointing arrows. At the bottom right of the main content area is a blue 'Start' button. The footer of the page shows the 'Responsible' section, which is currently empty.

Fig 4.7.4: Course example: Fundamentals of Artificial Intelligence

Fig 4.7.5: Subjects overview with AI and Machine Learning selected

Fig 4.7.6: Subjects example: Machine Learning

Fig 4.7.7: Software overview

20:48 Sun 12 Jan digipedia.tudelft.nl

DigiPedia

Installing Ladybug Tools 0/3

Installing Ladybug Tools

Installing, updating, and removing Ladybug Tools, Radiance and Open Studio

In order to be able to effectively run the Ladybug & Honeybee simulations, you should have the following software installed in your computer.

Ladybug is an analysis tool which is used in Grasshopper. It allows you to extract EnergyPlus Weatherdata from a wide range of locations. The data can be related to temperature, wind, humidity etc. Ladybug will enable you to get a good insight into the weather conditions throughout the year at your building location. The tool is used in the early stages of design so the weather data can be taken into account in the design decisions.

Ladybug Tools

TU Delft always tries to keep installation manuals up-to-date. Unfortunately, this is not always possible. If this tutorial, for any reason, does not follow the available steps in your situation, take a look at the [installation manual of Ladybug](#).

Needed software

To install the Ladybug Tools you need the following:

- Rhino & Grasshopper version 6 or 7

Fig 4.7.8: Software example: Ladybug

Fig 4.7.9: Lab overview

Fig 4.7.10: Lab example: LAMA lab

5. Concluding remarks

A broad spectrum of potentially useful courses exists that can facilitate the NEB community in obtaining digital skills and literacy. These courses range from simple tutorials on how to use a specific tool to code-writing courses that enable people to develop tools themselves.

The target group, often referred to as the “NEB community,” may be too narrowly defined if our aim is to upskill the construction ecosystem. In that case, we deal with a multi-language challenge ranging from vocational to academic levels. No out-of-the-box software platform existed to meet such requirements.

For this reason, TU Delft, a leader in Architecture and the Built Environment, started to develop an open-source solution based on the principles of open education: DigiPedia. It also offers a coherent training programme.

The aim is to deploy this system for the New European Bauhaus Academy, which is being prepared by the NEBA Alliance. Three out of four DigiNEB partners are members of this follow-up consortium. It is a robust way to secure the sustainability of the work outlined in this report.

List of Figures

Fig 4.7.1: Digipedia landing page

Fig 4.7.2: Overview of the four categories of tutorials in DigiPedia

Fig 4.7.3: Course overview with Master courses selected

Fig 4.7.4: Course example: Fundamentals of Artificial Intelligence

Fig 4.7.5: Subjects overview with AI and Machine Learning selected

Fig 4.7.6: Subjects example: Machine Learning

Fig 4.7.7: Software overview

Fig 4.7.8: Software example: Ladybug

Fig 4.7.9: Lab overview

Fig 4.7.10: Lab example: LAMA lab

